

QUIZ**LAST NAME: EBONYI****FIRST NAME: AUGUSTINE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. In writing an essay, which of the following is not true?

- The Introduction opens with a discussion of the ‘general to specifics’ of a research question.
- The Conclusion moves from ‘specific to general’ of the discussion on the answer to the research question.
- The body should provide the answer to the research question without necessarily providing any examples or arguments.¹**
- In the Body, every paragraph should be concerned with a least one main idea that is stated in the ‘topic sentence’ and also contains an analysis component of answer to the research question.

¹EUCLID, ACA-401 Coursepack (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015), 4. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed January 28, 2020).

2. **In academic writing, which of the following is true?**

- It is not plagiarism when an inexperienced researcher uses a source and is unable to cite it.
- Citation is not necessary when the information to be cited is empirical or is well known in the public domain.²**
- Word and Zotero are equally good for use in both bibliography and footnote referencing.
- Regarding in-text citation, both endnote and footnote serve the same purpose, only that endnotes are shorter in length.

3. **Every research is associated with a research question that requires an answer. In this context, all of the following are true, except one**

- In the academic world of humanities and social sciences, this kind of question is considered a ‘conceptual’ question.
- In the business world, this kind of question is considered an ‘applied’ question.³**
- A research hypothesis needs to be supported by relevant reasons and evidence for it to become a ‘research claim’.
- A research hypothesis usually helps to guide the type of information collected during a literature search.

4. **Concerning research arguments, which of the following is not true?**

- An argument supported by a ‘warrant’ is less likely to be trusted.

² EUCLID, 30-31.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 17.

- ‘Warrant’ and ‘evidence’ are essentially the same thing.**⁴
- A ‘reason’ is something that may not be referenced/cited.
- The steps in building an argument are: state the claim, then its reasons, followed by the evidence supporting the reasons.

5. **Concerning citations, which of the following is correct?**

- Properly and accurately citing a source does not guarantee against plagiarism.
- Modifying and using only just a few words or an idea of an author without citing the author is usually not a problem.
- Digital object identifier (DOI) alone is more reliable than Uniform resource locator (URL) alone.**⁵
- Presence of accessed date in a citation is proof that the citation is accurate.

6. **In notes-bibliography citation, notes and bibliography are different in all of the following ways, except**

- In notes, the author’s first name is mentioned first whereas in the bibliography the surname comes first.
- Notes are indented normally like other texts while the bibliography is indented with the first line flushed left.
- In notes, parentheses are used to enclose facts of the publication, but in bibliography entries, they are not.

⁴ Turabian, 41-42.

⁵ Ibid., 88.

In bibliography, the elements are separated by commas, but in notes, they are separated by a period.⁶

7. **In the Chicago editorial style, which of the following is true?**

- Graphics refer to only graphs.
- Graphics refer to graphs and tables.
- Independent variables are usually placed in the column heads.
- If in a sentence both a comma and a question mark or a dash is needed, omit the comma.⁷**

8. **A dissertation proposal should cover the following main areas**

- Introduction, literature review, methods and budget.
- Introduction, literature review, methods, and appendices that include consent form and ethical approval.
- Introduction, literature review and methods.⁸**
- Introduction, literature review, methods, study design and timeline.

9. **Some qualitative research traditions include which of the following**

- Ethnography, phenomenology, grounded theory, narrative research, hermeneutics and case study.⁹**

⁶ Turabian, 92.

⁷ Ibid., 179.

⁸ Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 18-19.

⁹ Ibid., 1

- Case study, phenomenology, social constructivism and pragmatism.
- Social constructivism, pragmatism, post-positivism, narrative research and case study.
- Social constructivism, pragmatism, post-positivism, ontology and methodology.

10. **The difference between qualitative research and quantitative research include all of the following, except**

- Qualitative research is about generating ideas, while quantitative research is about testing ideas.
- In the data collection process, the researcher is detached from the participants (not actively involved) in qualitative research while in quantitative research, the researcher is bonded with the participants (actively involved).¹⁰**
- In terms of questionnaires, the questions are usually open-ended in qualitative research, whereas the questions are closed-ended in quantitative research.
- The results of qualitative studies are geared towards transferability to other settings while those of quantitative studies are geared towards generalisability to other settings.

¹⁰ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 13-15.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.